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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

Education provides skills, knowledge and expertise necessary for influencing positive change. It plays a crucial leadership role in developing the capacity of learners to self-organize and participate in the process that enables them to better understand, innovate, recover and adapt in the face of increasing climate uncertainty. In Kenya, the government has considered the positive relationship between adult literacy and socio-economic development and invested in the revival of the programme with the hope of re-engineering it to help in solving problems bedeviling humanity. In Vihiga County, the government had invested heavily to improve the productivity of the beneficiaries in various spheres of development, like addressing the negative effects of climate change. Despite all these, there is still the problem of degradation of forests in the area. The study, established that the beneficiaries of the programme were rarely using the knowledge and skills learnt in the programme to involve in activities that mitigate climate change and effectively adapt in the face of the changes. The programme, therefore, plays a very minimal role in helping the beneficiaries to mitigate and adapt to climate change.

Key words: Adult literacy, climate, mitigation, adaptation.

INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

As the education sector interventions facilitate the eradication of poverty, ignorance, illiteracy and disease which were identified at independence in Kenya as impediments to national development, adult education and literacy programmes enable adult learners to fully participate in socio-economic development activities. Here, they acquire skills for better understanding of environmental issues and for mitigating the effects of climate change. This is supported by the fact that, those who had benefitted from the literacy programme have made gains in socio-economic development (Republic of Kenya, 2003).

In the Vihiga County where the study was conducted, and where the government had also spent US\$ 25,031.25, there were 2,603 adult learners in the adult literacy programme by 2010. This was, besides other benefits, meant to improve the learning environment and to help learners to realize tangible returns like engagement in socio-economic activities that mitigate and coping with the effects of climate change (DACE, 2010). The skills learnt were expected to help in the reclamation of the highly degraded forests on the hills around Maseno and Mahanga and the areas bordering the Kakamega forest, which is the home to a National Reserve and hundreds of indigenous bird species. The Kakamega forest had for a long time been under great threat due to excessive human activities like charcoal burning, encroachment by farmers, fuel wood collection and haphazard felling of trees. These activities have invariably interfered with the air and rainfall patterns in the area. Some rivers that cause flooding in Budalangi flood plains near Lake Victoria also pass through this area (Aluang'a, 2009).

Vihiga also lies between the highly degraded Kisumu and Siaya Counties and the high potential Nandi and Kakamega Counties that have the Kakamega rainforest; and it should be seen as a *buffer* between these zones. Since the population here is also highly literate (73.3%), this should positively be reflected in the activities aimed at sound environmental management (Republic of Kenya, 2006).

The **Objective** of the study was to determine the extent to which adult literacy learners used eco-friendly technologies and practices the skills acquired to mitigate and adapt to the effects of climate change. The study was guided by the “*production function*” theory where the inputs in form of teachers, funding and relevant reading materials are processed to influence learner achievement and produce desired outputs or returns (Vaizey, 2011). The use of this theory had found that the teaching and learning processes as well as the capacity of teachers, their attitudes and motivation, learners’ motivation and relevance and quality of education offered and the family backgrounds, the socio-economic factors and learners’ immediate environment were important determinants of learner achievement. In the learning centres, according to Psacharopoulos and Woodhall (1997), the *input* and *process* variables determine whether learners will achieve the desired *outputs* (benefits).

In other parts of the world, the human activity has been found to be the main cause of rapid increase in global average temperatures over the past several decades due to the burning of fossil fuel and aerosols and cement manufacture to fulfill both survival and development needs. These, together with land use, animal agriculture and deforestation emit CO₂ and methane gases that deplete the protective ozone layer, thereby affecting climate (<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/climatechange>, 2009). Climate change is therefore principally man-made and is happening faster than earlier assumed and its impact is seen in Kenya in the form of great droughts, floods and agricultural problems ([http:// news.co.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/sciences/nature/upload](http://news.co.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/sciences/nature/upload) Wikipedia.org, 2009). The country’s vulnerability to climate change is due to its low capacity to respond and adapt. In Vihiga, the impact of the climate change is seen in the learners’ environment through irregular and unpredictable rainfall patterns that disrupt planting and harvesting seasons, droughts, famine, floods and high disease prevalence, especially malaria which never used to affect people living in cold places. It has also led to rising cases of insecurity due to intercommunity conflicts over the diminishing resources ([www/bbc/climate change. 23.11.09](http://www.bbc.com/news/health-231109)).

METHODOLOGY

Research design: Descriptive survey research design was used to gather factual information and to determine the status and nature of the situation and to get the opinions, attitudes, preferences and perceptions of the people on the specific measures that the learners had taken to mitigate the effects of climate change.

Study area: Vihiga County lies along the Equator between 34⁰ 30mins E and 35⁰0min E, and 0⁰ 15mins N and 0⁰5mins S. in the western part of Kenya. It borders the Counties of Kisumu to the East, Nandi to the North-east, Kakamega to the West and Siaya to the South-south west. The 2009 Kenya Population and Housing Census had put the County’s population at 554,622 (Republic of Kenya, 2009). The population of the study area consisted of the 2,603 present learners, 4 District Adult Education Officers, 8 Divisional Adult Education Supervisors, and 61 teachers. The study also covered 20 past learners and 20 non-beneficiaries of the literacy programme.

Sampling: *Saturated sampling technique* was used to select the districts and officers but *simple random sampling* was used to select 120 learners, 40 homes, 20 centres and 35 teachers with the help of a table of random numbers (Bogdan & Biklem, 2003). This method was also used to select 40 homes of the learners that had not been covered for observation of the activities in their homes. For the past learners of the programme, *snowball sampling* techniques was used to select 20 past beneficiaries that were to be involved in the research. 20 non-beneficiaries of the programme to act as control were selected by use of purposive followed by simple random sampling technique.

Reliability of the tools: The tools were pre-tested. Using reliability analysis scale (*alpha*), there was split-half method followed by the determination of the *correlation coefficient* using Pearson Product Moment Correlation to determine the relationship between the two groups of scores *x*, *y*) so as to check on the consistency of the data.

$$r = \frac{\sum xy}{\sqrt{(\sum x^2)(\sum y^2)}}$$

Here *r*, is the relationship, *x* is the 1st half and *y* the 2nd half.

Data was collected with questionnaires, interview and observation schedules and cameras and analyzed using descriptive statistics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study found the following:

a) Improved use of technology

Although Vihiga County was endowed with immense natural resources which could improve her economy, the County was still finding itself faced with acute shortage of materials. This may be related to what Caillods (2008) had implied that, where a widening gap appears between the needs of society and the level of production, and between demand and supply, there is need to align or drastically re-model the new development conditions imposed by the scientific and technological revolution.

Planning for adaptation to climate change in the County therefore points to the need for re-afforestation programmes with climate-smart species and integrated land use and activities to improve the use of technology. To eliminate or reduce the risk of climate change to human life and property, both policy instruments and technology must be used in the context of sustainable development. The requirements to assure a high adaptive capacity therefore include a high degree of access to technology options, well-designed adaptation strategies and a system for dissemination of climate change and adaptation information.

The programme had also tried to promote local initiatives, develop awareness and translate activities that promote climate change mitigation and adaptation into action. However, these projects targeted mainly the reversal of environmental degradation through reforestation and land reclamation. The skills that the learners had acquired and which can help to mitigate the effects of climate change included those of energy saving. This is one of the initiatives used in the adult literacy programme to impart skills and knowledge to reduce vulnerability to the effects of climate change. This was found to be done by disseminating information on the use of renewable energy and promoting the development of new energy-saving technologies such as:

i) *Energy-saving stoves and jikos*

This was found to include the use of wood **saving stoves** and *jikos* (Plate 1a and 1b) that are important in the reduction in the cutting down of trees for energy purposes. This has the advantage of increasing efficiency in the use of wood fuel and other natural sources by households. This initiative is destined to help promote the regeneration of vegetation, and in particular, the trees (DVV, 2011). One of the skills learnt from the adult literacy programme which the learners were found to be using, is the making of fireless cookers (**4.8%**), especially at Gahumbwa adult education class in Sabatia district and at Emmakhwenje adult class in Emuhaya. These cookers were being used by the learners to cook their foodstuff with as little fuel as possible because the hot food still in the process of being cooked was removed and put into specially made baskets where it continued to be cooked without any fuel being used. The other is the skill of molding energy-saving *jikos* (**9.6%**) which use very little fuel wood to cook the food. The study found the evidence that a great majority of the beneficiaries of the literacy programme still harvested the trees for fuel wood. The small percentages of those using fireless cookers (**4.8%**) and those using energy-saving *jikos* (**9.6%**) is testimony of the extent to which the learners have adopted the necessary technologies for saving energy in the County. None of the learners were however found to be using any other green energy sources such as biomass, solar and wind to generate energy.

Plate 1a: Energy saving jikos

Plate 1b: Fireless cookers

ii) Biogas

An understanding of the need to act on and adapt to a changing climate may offer solution to turn waste into energy in the area. This may include design and construction of biogas plants for domestic households, farms, institutions and industrial processing ventures. Use of biogas can help in utilizing various wastes for the production of much needed and environmentally positive energy and nutrient-rich bio-fertilizer whilst at the same time providing a means for necessary waste treatment. This would mean that all resources are utilized efficiently and responsibly in order to ensure sustainable development (Republic of Kenya, 2011 p.10). Expanded access to biogas technology will ensure that Kenyans access energy that is affordable and environmentally friendly.

iii) Solar energy

The use of **Solar energy** could have been very ideal because as petroleum and electricity demand rises in homes, schools and cottage industries to power light, TVs, vaccine refrigerators and small appliances, solar electricity is a realistic alternative to costly extensions of grid power or generators (Smart Solar, 2011). Solar lantern is cheap to maintain and can save about 10-30% of household incomes spent on hazardous and low quality fuel-based lighting products that emit green house gases. Solar can provide cost-effective lighting solutions that replace kerosene and candles. It has been found that the poor burn US \$ 17 billion of kerosene each year in lanterns to light their homes although the light from kerosene lamps has a low intensity and makes it difficult for children to study, affecting literacy and education and minimizes productive working hours (Smart Solar, 2011 p.7). It provides quality, affordable and safe lighting to the people living in areas not connected to the electric grid, promote green energy as they do not produce any smoke that contributes to accumulation of carbon in the atmosphere (Mugambi, 2009).

b) Afforestation and selling seed to generate income

The study revealed that **28.6%** of the learners had tree nurseries from where they got seedlings which they were selling to generate funds for personal and domestic use. Learners also reported that they had acquired skills of treeplanting (**44%**) which they were using to involve in environmental conservation, although there was little evidence that they tendered the seedlings to plant (Plate. 2a). The afforestation programmes by the learners show clear attempts to recover formerly forested areas that had been lost due to logging, charcoal burning and poor farming practices. Afforestation and agro-forestry initiatives therefore present an opportunity for carbon sequestration that will in the long run reduce global warming, even in a small area. It also helps to improve forest management (Oywa, 2009). The trees planted by the learners in their afforestation activities included cypress, eucalyptus, mangoes, avocados, guava and indigenous trees.

Plate 2a: Tree nursery at Maseno

Plate 2b: Kakamega forest

c). Sustainable agriculture and Integrated land use

To adapt and mitigate the effects of climate change through sustainable agriculture, the following can be utilized:

i) Organic agriculture

As the use of inorganic fertilizers has drastically declined due to energy crisis, and as sustainable crop production requires judicious use of inputs, the organic farming, especially the use of animal manure has to be promoted. The study found that as a result of the skills learnt at the centres, 15.8% of the learners were practicing mulching, 17.6% were using poultry manure, 51% used cowshed manure and 4.8% used compost manure on their farms. The use of organic manure helps to increase microbial activities and hence increased soil fertility. It has been found that, animal manure increases taproot growth and dry root weight. It significantly increases crop yield and soil properties due to increased availability of N and P (Maerere *et al*, 2001). The acquisition of knowledge and skills on organic farming was also undertaken by organizing adult learners and other members of the community to make study visits to successful farmers who were already using these modern methods.

ii) Sustainable animal production

In response to climate change, communities will find it difficult to keep their livestock as a harsher climate will reduce the amount of water and pasture available and try to keep fewer high grade animals that they are able to cater for. Farmers may have to be encouraged to try to keep hardy varieties or species of livestock that are somewhat drought-resistant. These may include **camels** or **goats** (Walubengo, 2009).

It was found that attempts were made at the **Emmakhwenje** Adult literacy and Community Learning Resource Centre (CLRC) to introduce **dairy goat** farming to the community through the learners of the centre. They kept hybrid male goats to improve the local herds into bigger and healthier animals that fetch more when sold than indigenous breeds (Plate 3). The goats were a drought-resistant variety and were bred and their kitten given to learners. They also produced milk which the owners sold to generate income. Goats also give **milk** which help to improve the health of families as goat milk is more nutritious and has medicinal value (Ombuor, 2009). Goat keeping is therefore a contingency measure to cushion against drought and food insecurity.

Plate 3: Dairy goat at Emmakhwenje CLRC

iii) Sustainable crop production

The key to coping with climate change is to invest in sustainable agriculture to raise productivity and this also helps in diversifying the economy to create employment opportunities. In Kenya, official statistics indicate that some 10m people were facing food shortages in 2009 due to drought that occasioned massive crop failures in 2008 and 2009 (Opiyo, 2009). Sustainable crop production can be assured if the farmers are given necessary skills to enable them prevent soil degradation, that is a significant problem that limits agricultural productivity and to use early maturing and drought-resistant crops like cassava which do not need large quantities of water. It also involves the use of innovative irrigation and other appropriate farming systems. The learners used various skills as proof to the

invaluable returns to education they had got, especially at the adult literacy centres. These were found to include the following:

iv) Drought-tolerant crops/ climate smart species

The study revealed that **14.7%** of the learners had planted drought-resistant crops such as millet and sorghum, peas and beans (**2.5%**). Others still planted early maturing horticultural crops (**25%**) such as cowpeas and tomatoes that take only a few weeks to mature. Other drought-resistant crops grown were found to be bananas (**5%**), cassava (**21.3%**), (Plate 4) sweet potatoes (**17.7%**), guava and avocado (**1.3%**) and even Napier grass that were being used for feeding livestock. What was seen here was a clear case of diversified farming just as had been seen in Kericho where, climate change seen through increased rainfall and temperatures was in the process of rendering tea-growing areas unsuitable. To adapt to such conditions, the farmers, according to Tirop (2011), have to be trained on how to cope and to consider crop diversification in order to reduce the dangers of complete harvest loss due to extreme weather and pests. These are crops that may be sustainable under predictable weather. They have also to reduce deforestation and to provide alternative sources of energy other than depending on wood fuel that leads to more deforestation. Farmers were also being advised to strengthen sustainable tea practices and develop tea planting materials that can tolerate water stress, pests and diseases.

Plate 4: Cassava garden near Luanda, Emuhaya

d) Water harvesting

Global warming is taking a toll on water sources and bodies. Sustainable water **management** and **harvesting** is therefore a key mitigating factor in the face of unprecedented scarcity of water. Quality clean water is a basic necessity and it enhances the quality of living by curbing several water-borne diseases. Water for domestic use can be harvested by digging or constructing pans, or building sand dams on seasonal rivers to use for **watering livestock** and even for domestic use or irrigation (*The Standard, 2009*). Rainwater may also be harvested using various sizes or types of containers. The rain water is especially clean and good for domestic use. Water harvesting will also provide ready income (cash) for households through the sale of water directly to neighbours, sale of agricultural produce as well as seedlings grown in nurseries through small-scale irrigation.

e) Integrated land use

To ensure increased productivity, learners who were also farmers were using practices that increase soil fertility. This included use of ecologically compatible farming methods and crop diversification. The study found that residents in the area practiced both livestock and crop farming. This was seen by the fact all of the learners who reared cattle

were also crop farmers. Also, some (75%) of the learners practiced agro-forestry due to scarcity of available land as they did not have extra land to plant trees. About 25% of the learners were involved in small-scale bucket irrigation projects where they grew mostly vegetables along the streams. The study also found that as a result of the skills learnt at the centres, 9.8% of the learners were involved in zero-grazing and mulching (15.8%). To ensure improved soil fertility, they were using poultry manure (17.6%), cowshed manure (51%) and compost manure (4.8%) on their farms to increase the productivity of their farms.

i) Bee keeping

The study found that in areas close to the forests, particularly those areas bordering the Kakamega forest around Hamisi- Kaimosi and along the riverbanks near Maseno and Emuhaya, some of the learners had put the skills of bee-keeping into practice as 1.3% practiced bee-keeping. The prospects of bee-keeping was also being promoted by the Kenya Wildlife Services and this had seen bee-keeping, silkworm rearing and planting of medicinal plants as important non-destructive Income-Generating Activities around the forest (Obala & Okwayo, 2009).

ii) Fish farming

Although there had been attempts to introduce fish farming (Plate 5) as an important venture in adaptation to the effects of climate change, very few people in the County; only 1.3% of the people practiced it. Fishponds were found at Hamisi Community Learning Resource Centre in Hamisi, Magina Community Learning Resource Centre and at the Idunya Adult Literacy Centre in Sabatia district. Through fish farming, the adult literacy programme therefore made some very important contributions towards mitigation and adaptation to climate change. This was evident particularly at the centres where there were several projects from which the learners were expected to get necessary practical skills to be applied at their homes. It was however found that only on very few occasions did the learners practiced what they had learnt at the centres back in their homes. On many occasions still, non-beneficiaries of the adult literacy programme did even better than those who had earlier benefited from, or were currently benefitting from the programme. At Emmakhwenje CLRC, besides having dairy goat and energy saving *jiko* projects, the learners also planted banana at the centre as a demonstration for learners and visitors to learn from and get the skills of planting high yielding bananas. The skills learnt were expected to be used by individual learners in their homes to plant their bananas to generate for them funds.

Plate 5: A fish pond at Hamisi Community Learning Resource Centre

Sustainable practices in agriculture may therefore help to improve the livelihoods of families besides helping them to adapt to increasingly unpredictable weather, and to reduce emissions of carbon dioxide and other green house gases. On its part, through farm diversification and building soil fertility with organic matter, organic agriculture has a

strong potential for building resilient food systems in the face of uncertainties. Organic agricultural systems in developing countries like Kenya can help achieve equal or even higher yields as compared to the current conventional practices, which translate into a potentially important option for food security and sustainable livelihoods for the rural poor in times of climate change (Kenya Organic Agricultural Network, 2011, p.16).

CONCLUSION

In Kenya, as $\frac{3}{4}$ of the land is semi-arid and the climate still becoming hotter, necessary action must be taken to train the populations to cope with climatic changes that have already happened and have caused serious socio-economic problems. Appropriate technologies have therefore to be adopted by citizens while making use of the most traditional knowledge and practices. The people's livelihoods have to be diversified to cope with emerging climate change-related issues and its implications.

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